

Inorganic Ireland 2025

Report by: C. Papatriantafyllopoulou

Event Date: 23/05/2025

Venue: University of Galway,
Human Biology
Building, Galway

Event Type: Symposium

Report received: 30/05/2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15556249

<http://zenodo.org/communities/ice/>

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GAILLIMHE
UNIVERSITY
OF GALWAY

Organising Committee: C. Papatriantafyllopoulou (Chair),^a C. Marmion,^b G. Morgan,^c M. Muldoon,^d A. McDonald,^e

^a University of Galway; ^b Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland; ^c University College Dublin; ^d Queen's University Belfast; ^e Trinity College Dublin

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, RSC Dalton Transactions, Complete Laboratory Solutions

Summary

The Inorganic Ireland Symposium 2025 took place on Friday, 23rd May at the University of Galway and brought together over 50 participants from across Ireland and beyond for a vibrant and engaging one-day meeting dedicated to inorganic chemistry. The symposium aimed to strengthen national collaborations, create space for early-career researchers to share their work, and celebrate the diversity and excellence of inorganic chemistry research in Ireland.

The programme featured a rich mix of scientific contributions, including two plenary lectures delivered by Prof. Richard Layfield (University of Sussex, UK), recipient of the 2023 RSC Corday-Morgan Prize, and Prof. Stuart James (Queen's University Belfast), recipient of the 2025 ICI David Brown Award. A heartfelt tribute lecture by Dr Andrea Erxleben (University of Galway) was also included, honouring the memory of Prof. Pat McArdle, to whom the symposium was dedicated. The scientific sessions further included 3 plenary-level talks, 14 oral presentations, 5 flash talks, and 18 poster presentations, with strong representation from postgraduate students and postdoctoral researchers across Irish institutions.

Two Early Career Poster Prizes were awarded to highlight

excellent research from emerging scientists. The recipients of the poster prizes are Bhawna Kumari (UL) and Judit Fodor (TCD).

The symposium was generously supported by the Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC) Local Section Republic of Ireland, Dalton Transactions, the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland (ICI), and Complete Laboratory Solutions (CLS) and was organised by a national committee chaired by Dr Constantina Papatriantafyllopoulou and including Prof. Celine Marmion, Prof. Mark Muldoon, Dr Grace Morgan and Dr Aidan McDonald. The organisers are grateful to all attendees, contributors, and sponsors for making the event a memorable success.

Attendees

The symposium welcomed approximately 55 attendees, representing a broad mix of academic levels (undergraduates to senior academics), institutions across Ireland and beyond, and diverse cultural backgrounds. Gender representation was balanced across speakers and audience, with strong participation from early-career researchers and international attendees.

Target audience: academics undergraduates, postgraduates, retired members,

List of speakers

Richard Layfield (University of Sussex)
 Stuart James (Queen's University Belfast)
 Andrea Erxleben (University of Galway)

Fabio Santani (Trinity College Dublin)
 Aibhe Boran (University of Galway)
 Soumya Mukherjee (University of Limerick)
 Darragh McHugh (University of Galway)
 Federica Brescia (University of Galway)
 Olivia Breed (University College Dublin)
 Joseph Byrne (University College Dublin)
 Tandra Ghoshal (Trinity College Dublin)
 Joshua Thorogood (Trinity College Dublin)

Proceedings**Morning Session – Chair: Constantina****Papatriantafyllopoulou**

Richard Layfield (University of Sussex) – **2023 RSC Corday-Morgan Prize Lecture:** Masked Oxidation States in Lanthanide Organometallic Chemistry Fabio

Fabio Santani (Trinity College Dublin) – Triggering Weak Exchange Coupling Interactions in Metalloporphyrin-Based Quantum Logic Gates

Aibhe Boran (University of Galway) – Structural Elucidation and Morphological Exploration of Low Crystallinity Fe-based MCOFs for CO₂ Reduction Reactions

Midday Session – Chair: John Simmie

Soumya Mukherjee (University of Limerick) – Crystal Engineering of Azolate Coordination Networks for Cleaning Air and Freshwater

Andrea Erxleben (University of Galway) – Crystallography in Galway – In Memoriam Professor Patrick McArdle

Afternoon Session – Chair: Grace Morgan

Stuart James (Queen's University Belfast) – **ICI David Brown Award 2025 Lecture**

Darragh McHugh (University of Galway) – OnG7: A Metal–Organic Framework for Potential Chemotherapeutic Delivery in Breast Cancer Treatment

Federica Brescia (University of Galway) – Design and Development of Gold(III)-Glycoconjugates as Antiviral Agents against SARS-CoV-2

Olivia Breed (University College Dublin) – Two Centuries of Research and All I Got Was These Polymorphs: Diverse Polymorphism in Metal Ammonia Oxalate Hydrate Coordination Polymers

Final Session – Chair: Diego Montagner

Joseph Byrne (University College Dublin) – Glycoconjugate Metal Complexes as Anti-Adhesives against Pathogens

Tandra Ghoshal (Trinity College Dublin) – Fabrication of Sub-20 nm MoS₂ Horizontal Nanowire Arrays by Block Copolymer Assisted Inclusion Method

Joshua Thorogood (Trinity College Dublin) – Synthetic Magnesium Tetrapyrrole Radicals for Mechanistic Studies of Photosystem II

Prizes

Two poster prizes were awarded at the Inorganic Ireland Symposium 2025, with a focus on recognising excellent research and presentation skills among early career researchers. The recipients of the prizes are Judit Fodor (TCD) and Bhawna Kumari (UL)

Figure 1. Recipients of the poster prizes: Bhawna Kumari and Judit Fodor.

Figure 2. Prof. Stuart James receives the 2025 ICI David Brown Award.

About the ICI David Brown Award

This award was established in 2014 to honour Professor David Brown of University College Dublin in recognition of his enormous contribution to inorganic chemistry

both nationally and internationally. Professor Brown, together with Professor Bill Davis (TCD) hosted the International Conference on Coordination Chemistry (ICCC) in UCD in 1974. With some funds remaining, Professor Brown set up what became known as the Greystones weekend meetings, which were held in the LaTouche Hotel in Greystones and later in a more formal setting, in Maynooth University, hosted by Dr Malachy McCann every three years until 2005. This was re-launched as a one-day *Inorganic Ireland Symposium* and has been held approximately every two years since then. A highlight of this symposium is the presentation of the ICI David Brown award to a colleague who has made an outstanding contribution to inorganic chemistry.

Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge the support of all sponsors as listed above, and the host institution, the University of Galway, for providing the venue and facilities. We would like to extend our appreciation to the session chairs, speakers, and all attendees for contributing to the vibrant atmosphere of the event. Special thanks to Manal Alrashidi, Constantinos G. Efthymiou, Darragh McHugh, and Ben Mohan for their pivotal role in organising and running the symposium.

Previous Events in this Series

The *Inorganic Ireland* symposium series has run approximately every second year in recent times. It is the successor of the Greystones Meetings, set up by Professor David Brown in the 1970s. Reports on some recent symposia are given below:

Inorganic Ireland 2023 (Trinity College Dublin), Programme available on Institute of Chemistry of Ireland website, <https://www.chemistryireland.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Inorganic-Ireland-Symposium-2023-Programme.pdf> (Accessed 30/05/2025)

Inorganic Ireland 2021 (Online). *Irish Chemical News*, **2021**, 5, 34

Inorganic Ireland 2018 (Queen's University Belfast), *Irish Chemical News*, **2019**, 1, 10.

Inorganic Ireland 2017 (Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland), *Irish Chemical News*, **2017**, 3, 18.